

Through- thickness Reinforcement of Composites : Z-pinning, Stitching, and 3D weaving

L.G.Stringer and M.J.Hiley

*Future Systems Technology, QinetiQ, Ively Road, Farnborough Hampshire, GU14 0LX, UK,
www.qinetiq.com*

ABSTRACT : This paper brings together several experimental research projects carried out at QinetiQ involving z-pinning, stitching, and 3-D weaving. These have been investigated to assess the potential for developing through-thickness reinforcement in composite laminates, in order to improve the resistance to impact damage from a falling object or projectile.

The increasing use of resin infusion manufacturing processes, such as RTM and RFI, allow such through-thickness reinforcement methods to be incorporated into the composite relatively easily. The effect of z-pinning on in-plane properties, impact and fracture toughness has been investigated. This work has also included the effect of z-pinning at the interface between T-stiffeners and composite skins. For through-thickness stitching, a large range of stitching parameters has been assessed with NCF fabrics, to establish whether an optimum set of stitching parameters exists. Finally, for 3-D woven composites, a large range of 3-D fabric architectures has been studied, with a similar objective of developing through-thickness reinforcement into the composite to improve its impact performance.

KEYWORDS: composites, through-thickness reinforcement, z-pinning, stitching, 3D weaving

INTRODUCTION

Most traditional fibre reinforced laminates, which have a layered 2-D fibre architecture, have relatively poor through-thickness mechanical properties. In addition, traditional composites suffer extensive damage by delamination when impacted by a falling object or projectile because of their low interlaminar fracture resistance. This damage can degrade the in-plane mechanical properties [1, 2] and is often considered the life limiting damage mode.

However, the increasing use of resin infusion manufacturing processes, such as RTM and RFI, allow through-thickness reinforcement methods such as stitching and 3-D woven fabrics to be incorporated into the composite relatively easily. This should assist the development of more impact resistant and damage tolerant composites.

Z-pinning is a through-thickness reinforcement technique that has, to date, been mostly investigated in prepreg materials, but is now also being considered for resin infusion techniques using dry preforms. It consists of narrow pins (of precured composite) spaced evenly in a sacrificial crushable foam layer, which are driven ultrasonically through the thickness of the fibre lay-up.

3-D fibre preforms, in which fibres extend in the through-the-thickness direction, have received attention over the last decade, and considerable research has been devoted to evaluating the

impact damage resistance and tolerance of fibre reinforced composites made with a 3-D fibre architecture [e.g. 3 – 6].

Stitched 2-D laminates have been reported to possess greatly improved interlaminar properties which are comparable with 3-D fibre reinforced composites produced by weaving [7]. Within this category of materials a notable example is the ‘non-crimp fabric’ (NCF) which maintains nominally straight fibres in the plies of the laminate. Through-thickness stitching of NCF preforms has the potential advantage of applying additional z-direction reinforcement to that already incorporated in each layer of the NCF fabric by the materials supplier.

This paper brings together several experimental research projects carried out at QinetiQ involving z-pinning, stitching and 3-D woven fabrics, which have all investigated the potential for developing through-thickness reinforcement in composite laminates.

The effect of z-pinning on in-plane properties, impact and fracture toughness has been investigated in carbon/epoxy prepreg. Cross sectioning of the laminates was used to assess the impact of the pins on the fibres within the laminate, with the aim of assessing the affect of the pins on the mechanisms of failure taking place.

In a separate study, from previous published research into through-thickness stitching it was apparent that there was no clear consensus on whether stitching improves impact resistance, and how far the in-plane properties are degraded; performance may be improved, degraded or remain unchanged. Therefore a large range of through-thickness stitching parameters were investigated for glass fibre and carbon fibre quasi-isotropic NCF lay-ups, to establish whether an optimum set of stitching parameters exists.

Finally, in a collaborative project on 3-D woven composites a large range of 3-D fabric architectures has been studied, with the same objective of developing through-thickness reinforcement into the composite to improve its impact performance. In-plane and impact properties were studied across 13 different carbon fibre and 11 glass fibre 3-D fabrics, which included orthogonal, angle interlock, and 3X architectures.

Z-PINNING

Manufacturing details

Composite laminates based on the carbon/epoxy system IM7/8552, were manufactured using 0.51mm diameter z-pins, with a 2% density. Additional specimens for compression after impact testing (CAI) were also manufactured with 0.28mm pins. A summary of tests performed and laminate configurations assessed are shown in table 1.

Test	Specimen gauge length/dimensions (mm)	Laminate Construction	Laminate configuration assessed
Plain tension	25 x 150	24 ply [(+0, -, 90) ₃] _S	N, L
Plain compression	25 x 150	24 ply [(+0, -, 90) ₃] _S	N, L
Compression after Impact	50 x 150	24 ply [(+0, -, 90) ₃] _S	N, L, S
Mode I (DCB)	25 x 200	24 ply [0 ₂ , +, -, 0, 90 ₂ , 0, -, +, 0 ₂] _S	N, L
Mode II (ENF)	25 x 200	24 ply [0 ₂ , +, -, 0, 90 ₂ , 0, -, +, 0 ₂] _S	N, L

N = No pins, L= Large diameter pins (0.51mm), S = Small diameter pins (0.28mm)

Table 1 Summary of test specimen dimensions

An ASTEX UAZ-1000 Gantry mounted z-pinning machine, see figure 1, was used to insert the z-pins into the laminates. Before inserting the z-pins all the laminates were preconsolidated to prevent the pins being left proud of the laminate surfaces after autoclaving.

Figure 1 Photograph of Z-pinning

The z-pins were supplied by the manufacturer mounted in a crushable foam preform. The principle of pin insertion involved crushing the foam preform containing the pins using the ultrasonic head on the equipment, thereby driving the pins into the uncured composite.

Figure 2 Schematic showing pin insertion

Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram of the z-pinning apparatus, that illustrates in more detail the insertion process. The action of the ultrasonic head caused localised heating of the pins and surrounding resin, reducing the viscosity of the latter, which assisted pin insertion.

The foam layer and protruding section of the pins remaining on the surface after z-pinning was subsequently removed by scoring the foam and shearing off the pins with a flat blade.

Mechanical testing

Both plain and impacted specimens were tested in tension and compression and a comparison made between pinned and unpinned laminates. Mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests were also performed to evaluate the effect of z-pinning on the initiation and propagation of delaminations.

Except where stated, all specimens were pinned across their entire surface area (with the exception of the end tabbed region) and tested in plain tension and compression. After end tabbing with glass fibre composite tabs, specimens were tested at a rate of 2mm/min in both compression and in tension. To prevent macro-buckling of the specimens tested in compression these specimens were supported along their length using anti-buckling guides.

In addition to conducting plain tests, impacted tests were also performed, the specimen dimensions for which are also shown in a table 1. An instrumented falling weight impactor, fitted with a 10mm hemi-spherical tup was used to impact the cured panels. Impacts were spaced approximately 100mm apart to prevent damage from adjacent impacts overlapping. All impacts were undertaken with a nominal energy of 9J.

The mode I and mode II fracture toughness was determined using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End Notched Flexure (ENF) test, respectively. Tests were performed according to ESIS procedures, on 24 ply specimens containing a 10µm mid-plane (PTFE) insert. Unlike conventional DCB and ENF tests, which are usually performed on unidirectional laminates, a [+ , 0 , - 90] laminate, containing a block of four 0° plies at the centre, was tested. A multidirectional laminates was chosen over a wholly unidirectional laminate, because of concerns that splitting might occur in the latter. The multidirectional laminate was also considered more representative of those used in structural elements. Specimens were designed so that a gap of approximately 10mm was left between the end of the starter film and the beginning of the pinned region. The gap was inserted to allow room for pre-cracking. With the DCB tests, crack propagation was initiated directly from the PTFE starter film by pulling them

in tension, the crack growing from an unpinned region into a pinned region. The mode II specimens were initially precracked in shear using a three point bending fixture. The crack tip was grown across the 10mm section of unpinned material, until it just reached the beginning of the pinned region. The specimen was then repositioned in the test fixture and loaded in an unstable configuration until the delamination grew. Using the failure load and corresponding displacement, the strain energy release rates G_{IC} and G_{IIC} were determined using beam theory.

Results

The results of the in-plane tests, performed on pinned and unpinned laminates, are shown in table 2. It was seen that z-pinning with the large diameter (0.51mm) pins reduced the tensile strength of the laminates considerably and also had a small detrimental effect on the compression properties. When the results of the Compression After Impact (CAI) results were studied the effect of pinning was seen to have a beneficial effect on the laminate properties. The CAI strength increased from 315.4 GPa in the plain laminates, to 371 GPa in the z-pinned laminates containing the smallest diameter pins.

Test type	Pin Size (mm)	Failure Stress (MPa)
Plain tension 24 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₃] _S	None 0.51	866.6 695.5
Plain compression 24 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₃] _S	None 0.51	574.7 544.9
Open hole tension* 24 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₃] _S	None 0.51	465.5 438.3
Compression after impact 24 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₃] _S	None 0.51 0.28	315.4 349.1 371.8

N = No pins, L= Large diameter pins (0.51mm), S = Small diameter pins (0.28mm)

Table 2 Summary of z-pinning results – In-plane tests

Tables 3 and 4 show the results of the interlaminar toughness tests performed using the DCB and ENF tests. A comparison of the mode I results showed that there was very little difference in energy required to initiate delamination growth between the pinned and unpinned laminate. When, however, the energy required to propagate the delamination was considered it was apparent that the z-pinned laminate performed much better.

Specimen Number	G_{IC} (J/m ²)*	Mean G_{IC} (J/m ²)	C.V (%)
CM7372-1	225.7		
CM7372-2	247.0		
CM7372-2	193.2		
CM7372-4	238.5	226.1	10.4
XA10985 (P)	180.7		
XA10986 (P)	229.0		
XA10987 (P)	231.5		
XA10988 (P)	192.3	208.4	12.3

(P) = Pinned samples (0.51mm pins), * corrected beam theory

Table 3 Summary of mode I test results

Specimen Number	G_{IIC} (J/m ²)*	Mean G_{IIC} (J/m ²)	C.V (%)
CM 1327-6	858.7		
CM 1327-7	873.8		
CM 1327-9	847.8		
CM 1327-10	871.2	862.9	1.4
XA1099-1 (P)	1210.6		
XA1099-3 (P)	885.0		
XA1099-4 (P)	1181.9		
XA1099-5 (P)	1051.1	1082.2	14.0
(P) = Pinned samples (0.51mm pins)			

Table 4 Summary of mode II test data

Figure 3 shows typical R-curves (G_{IC} versus crack length), obtained for the pinned and unpinned laminates, which illustrate how the energy required to drive the delamination forward rose dramatically in the z-pinned laminate, whilst the response of the unpinned material remained largely unchanged with crack length. When the mode II toughness G_{IIC} of unpinned and pinned laminates were compared it was clear that the inclusion of z-pins increased the toughness significantly. Since the ENF test gave only toughness data for the initiation of delamination growth, the effect of z-pinning on delamination propagation could not be assessed.

Figure 3 Graph showing G_{IC} versus Crack length for pinned and unpinned

To understand the differences in the behaviour observed between the pinned and unpinned laminates, cross sections through the pinned laminates were examined. Figures 4 and 5 shows a cross-section taken from the laminates containing 0.28mm and 0.51mm diameter pins, respectively. It was apparent from these cross sections that the larger pins caused significantly more distortion of the fibres than the smaller pins. The distortion of the fibres would have

Figure 4 Cross section of Z-pinned laminate (plan) showing fibre distortion caused by small pins (x20)

Figure 5 Cross section of Z-pinned laminate (plan) showing fibre distortion caused by large pins (x20)

almost certainly promoted fibre microbuckling around the pins under compression loading, resulting in premature failure. In figure 6 a cross-section taken along the length of a z-pin is shown. It was apparent that insertion of the pins caused significant fibre fracture and also the formation of resin rich areas. The fibre fracture around the z-pins would have provided initiation

sites for fracture under tensile loading, which would explain the reduced strength exhibited by the plain tension specimens.

Whilst z-pinning of plain specimens generally had a deleterious effect on their performance, the pinning of impacted laminates was clearly beneficial. The reason for this difference appeared to be attributable to improvements in delamination resistance of the impacted samples caused by insertion of the pins. In compression, the initiation of failure in impacted specimens is often controlled by the growth of delaminations

Figure 6 Cross section (side view) of Z-pinned laminate showing fibre fracture caused by large pins (x20)

and the z-pins would have helped to suppress this. The interaction between compressive failure mechanisms and delamination failure mechanisms is a complex one, which is heavily dependent upon the size and distribution of the pins. The state of the interface between the z-pins and surrounding matrix is also critical to the performance of the composite. Further studies to optimise and understand the interaction between the above mechanisms is required if z-pins are to be applied successfully to composite structures. A more detailed fractographic examination of the samples using electron microscopy is also required, to understand the complex mechanisms driving failure under different loading scenarios and z-pin configurations. In laminates based on woven fabrics, where there is already an inherent crimp in the load bearing fibres, the effect of pinning on plain compression strength may therefore be less significant.

STITCHING

The development of 3-D fibre preforms, in which fibres extend in the through-the-thickness direction, and associated technologies, have received considerable attention over the last decade. A great deal of research has been devoted to evaluating the impact damage resistance and tolerance of FRP composites made with a 3-D fibre architecture. The 3-D fibre preforms have been fabricated using a variety of textile processes such as weaving, knitting, braiding, and stitching [e.g. Dransfield et al 1993 and 1994, Bannister and Herszberg 1996, Crothers et al 1996]. The work described in this part of the paper concentrates on stitching and the performance of stitched laminates.

Generally, stitching is a unique process in that the stitched preform is not an integral structure, as the through-the-thickness yarn or tow is inserted into a traditional 2-D preform as a secondary process following fibre placement. Despite this difference, stitched laminates have been reported to possess greatly improved interlaminar properties which are comparable with 3-D FRP composites produced by weaving (Portanova 1994). This category of materials includes ‘non-crimp fabrics’ (NCF) which maintains nominally straight fibres in the plies of the laminate.

The through-thickness stitching that was of key interest in this project, however, was significantly thicker than that already present in NCF’s, and was inserted completely through the NCF fabric lay-up to form a dry preform. It was therefore termed ‘post-stitching’, to distinguish it from the much finer stitches included the NCF material by the fabric supplier.

Although advantages have been reported for through-thickness stitching, the findings of a comprehensive review at the start of the project showed that there was considerable discrepancy in reported results. It would appear that performance may be improved, or degraded or remain unchanged. For compressive properties, some studies report that there is no effect on in-plane properties with stitching; most report a significant degradation. The effect of stitch row orientation with loading direction remains unclear. Stitching may enhance ILSS at low stitch

densities, but at high stitch densities ILSS can be degraded. However, whilst through-thickness reinforcement currently has an unpredictable effect on in-plane properties, it can limit delamination, and benefit damage tolerance.

It is possible that much of this variation in these results is due to the different stitching parameters used in the various studies. The aim of the current work was therefore to study a variety of stitching parameters, using the same baseline NCF material, in order to identify whether a set of optimised stitching parameters exists. All lay-ups in this phase of the work were therefore quasi-isotropic (QI), using various Brunswick Technologies NCFs. Both glass and carbon fibre NCF's were investigated. The types of NCF used to produce the QI layup were selected to allow a large number of layer interfaces, in order to assess the effect of stitching on layups that were reasonably similar to multilayered prepreg material. The results reported here are for the following layup (designated A1) :-

Layup A1 + - / 0 / 90 / + - / 0 / 90 // 90 / 0 / - + / 90 / 0 / - +

All the laminates were resin transfer moulded using Hexcel RTM6 epoxy resin. No binder was used in the preforms, so that the true effect of post-stitching could be established. Binder additions could have had an additional effect, and may have led to inconsistencies. Furthermore, through-thickness post-stitching potentially provides an alternative method of preforming, eliminating the need for the addition of a binder in some cases.

Each RTM laminate measured 400 x 400mm in size, and was ultrasonically C-scanned to check for quality and voids, the latter always being less than 1%.

The post-stitching on the dry NCF preforms was carried out by Ellis Developments Ltd using a six-head high-speed embroidery machine. This enabled accurate positioning of all stitch positions by the use of an X-Y frame transfer. Post-stitching was investigated using both Kevlar and polyester sewing thread. Both high and low tension stitching was achieved by selecting a different type of stitch - standard lock stitch on bobbin in high tension, and modified lock stitch on bobbin in low tension.

The stitching parameters assessed were as follows :-

Stitching yarn	-	Kevlar and polyester
Yarn diameter	-	80 tex and 40 tex yarn
Pitch spacing	-	5mm and 10mm
Row spacing	-	5mm and 10mm
Stitch tension	-	High and low tension

These stitch parameters were investigated by combining them into six groups (designated from S1 to S6) :-

- S1 = 80 tex yarn ; 10mm pitch, 10mm row spacing ; high stitch tension
- S2 = 80 tex yarn ; 5mm pitch, 5mm row spacing ; high stitch tension
- S3 = 80 tex yarn ; 5mm pitch, 5mm row spacing ; low stitch tension
- S4 = 40 tex yarn ; 10mm pitch, 10mm row spacing ; high stitch tension
- S5 = 40 tex yarn ; 5mm pitch, 5mm row spacing ; high stitch tension
- S6 = 40 tex yarn ; 5mm pitch, 5mm row spacing ; low stitch tension

The designations of the post-stitched laminates combined the lay-up and stitching numbering e.g. A1G/S1K represents composite lay-up A1 with glass fibre NCFs, post-stitched using the S1 set of stitch parameters with Kevlar stitching yarn. 2.5.8 The stitching was always carried out in the longitudinal direction of the laminates (i.e. in the direction of the warp fibres in the fabrics).

All mechanical test methods were according to either ISO standards or CRAG specifications. (the latter was used for compression and compression after impact (CAI)).

The effects of the various post-stitching parameters on in-plane strength properties of the glass fibre QI NCF laminate are shown in Figures 7 and 8. Tensile strength was degraded only slightly by the presence of post-stitching (Figures 1 and 2), only amounting to about a 10% decrease in the worst case. With the finer Kevlar yarn there was no significant degradation.

Fig 7 Effect of various post-stitching parameters on tensile strength (a) warp direction (b) weft direction

However, the effect of post-stitching on in-plane compression strength in this QI laminate was surprising. In all cases post-stitching has increased the compression strength, and with the finer Kevlar yarn using the smallest stitch density (5mm x 5mm) strength has been increased by as much as 40%. This cannot be due to a simple hybrid effect from the stitching, as both Kevlar and polyester fibres both have a lower compression strength than glass.

An explanation for this behaviour lies in the effect of the post-stitching on microbuckling, the mechanism by which fibre reinforced composites fail under compression loading. It is possible that the post-stitches are assisting the ability of the reinforcing glass fibres to resist microbuckling. Since an strength increase is also seen with polyester as well as Kevlar stitching, it is unlikely to be due to the greater stiffness of the stitch, but it may be as a result of pinning of the load bearing fibres at regular intervals, with a corresponding increase in the compressive failure load.

Fig 8 Effect of various post-stitching parameters on compression strength (a) warp direction (b) weft direction

Figure 8a also includes results of compression-after-impact (CAI) tests (12.5mm hemi-spherical impactor at 25J) for the various post-stitching parameters for laminates. It can be seen that the increased compression strength in the undamaged composite, gained by post-stitching, has been almost totally lost again in the CAI strength results. Although virtually all of the sets of stitching parameters slightly increased CAI strength, there was not a large effect.

The reason for the laminates not retaining the increased compression strength when impacted is probably due to the post-stitches all being broken beneath the impactor. Therefore the increased resistance to microbuckling is locally lost at the site of damage.

3-D WEAVING

The aim of the project described in this part of the paper was to develop three-dimensional (3-D) woven fabrics, again in order to significantly improve the impact performance of continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites. 3-D fabrics have fibres woven in the through-thickness (z) direction, as well as in the plane (i.e. x and y directions) of the material. This provides stiffness and strength through the thickness of the laminate, and potentially should also increase its impact resistance and damage tolerance significantly. Furthermore, because the z-direction fibres can lock several fibre plies (layers) together, 3-D weaving allows the production of very thick multi-layer fabrics; this reduces the time required for fabrication of thick composite parts.

As well as orthogonal architectures, angle interlock, 3X, and 3X with warp stuffers were developed by the collaborating weaving company (Park Hill Textiles, Burnley). The warp yarn forms the 2-D planar construction and thus properties in the x-y plane are fixed. However, the size of the weft yarn can be selected to impart a range of properties from isotropic to pronounced in a principal direction. Customised software was also developed by the weaving company to allow CAD of 3-D weave architectures, the parameters of which were then directly input to the 3D weaving machine. Figures 9 shows the 3X and 3X + stuffers from the range of architectures developed :-

Fig 9 Computer generated diagrams of 3X and 3X+stuffers weave architectures produced by Park Hill Textiles (permission of Park Hill Textiles is acknowledged)

Both glass and carbon fibre 3-D fabrics were developed in the project, and the composite laminates were produced by resin transfer moulding.

Figure 10 shows the compression and CAI strength of a series of orthogonal 3D woven glass composites, with the proportion of z-fibre varying from 4% to 23%. The impact conditions used were again 25J with a 12.5mm hemi-spherical steel impactor. It can be seen that % loss in compression strength is decreased as the proportion of fibres in the z-direction increases. This is mainly because the compression strength in the undamaged state decreases, as the fibres are taken out of the warp direction to form z-direction fibres.

Fig 10 Effect of varying z-fibre content on orthogonal glass 3D woven composites

Further research required to optimise these types of through-thickness reinforced composite, but now that a large range of such fabrics are available this optimisation work can begin.

OVERALL CONCLUSIONS

Through-thickness reinforcement of advanced fibre reinforced composites is very complex, and varying results have been achieved, both in previous studies and also in those described in this paper. Therefore further research is required before the fundamentals can be fully understood. However, the reinforcement methods investigated here have shown that there is potential for improving impact resistance and damage tolerance without degrading the in-plane mechanical properties.

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